

Abstract

15
16 Estimating ocean biogeochemistry (BGC) parameters in Earth System Models is chal-
17 lenging due to multiple error sources and interlinked parameter sensitivities. Reducing the
18 temperature and salinity bias in the ocean physical component of the Norwegian Earth
19 System Model (NorESM) diminishes the BGC state bias at intermediate depth but leads
20 to a greater bias increase near the surface. This suggests that BGC parameters are tuned
21 to compensate for the physical ocean model biases. We successfully apply the iterative
22 ensemble smoother data assimilation technique to estimate BGC parameters in NorESM
23 with reduced bias in its physical ocean component. We estimate BGC parameters based
24 on the monthly climatological error of nitrate, phosphate, and oxygen in a coupled reanal-
25 ysis of NorESM that assimilates observed monthly climatology of temperature and salinity.
26 First, we compare the performance of globally uniform and spatially varying parameter es-
27 timations. Both approaches reduce BGC bias obtained with default parameters, even for
28 variables not assimilated in the parameter estimation (e.g., CO₂ fluxes and primary produc-
29 tion). While spatial parameter estimation performs locally best, it also increases biases in
30 areas with few observations, and overall performs poorer than global parameter estimation.
31 A second iteration further reduces the bias in the near-surface BGC with global parameter
32 estimation. Finally, we assess the performance of global estimated parameters in a 30-year
33 coupled reanalysis produced by assimilating time-varying temperature and salinity observa-
34 tions. This reanalysis reduces error by 10-20% for phosphate, nitrate, oxygen, and dissolved
35 inorganic carbon compared to a reanalysis done with default parameters.

Plain Language Summary

36
37 Earth System Models heavily rely on parametrization that accounts for unresolved
38 processes. Fine-tuning these numerous parameters is challenging because there are multiple
39 sources of error, and the parameters' sensitivities are interlinked. The ocean biogeochemistry
40 models are particularly challenging as they are heavily parameterized, and observations are
41 sparse. We show evidence that ocean biogeochemistry parameters in the Norwegian Earth
42 System Model that contributed to the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project have been
43 tuned to compensate for errors in the physical ocean model. Reducing these biases yields
44 sub-optimal performance in ocean biogeochemistry. Here, we demonstrate that data assim-
45 ilation (an iterative ensemble smoother) can provide a successful framework for re-tuning
46 such parameters within our system with ocean physical biases constrained. The method
47 can effectively reduce the mismatch between the modeled ocean biogeochemistry state and
48 the observations, even for variables not used in the estimation process. Performance with
49 estimated parameters and constrained bias in ocean physics achieves superior performance

50 than that done with the default version. The new parameter estimation method will be
51 instrumental in enhancing the performance of climate models.

52 **1 Introduction**

53 Earth system models (ESMs) have been key tools for answering fundamental questions
54 about our climate systems and include different components of the Earth System (e.g.,
55 atmosphere, ocean, land, sea ice, land ice ...). They also include an ocean biogeochemistry
56 (BGC) model, as BGC processes play a pivotal role in regulating the atmospheric carbon
57 dioxide concentration (e.g., Sabine et al., 2004; Sarmiento & Gruber, 2006). The ocean
58 biogeochemistry (BGC) is typically represented by key processes such as water column
59 carbon chemistry and lower trophic ecosystem, thus allowing us to study its feedback to the
60 climate and the impacts of climate change on the marine environment (Flato, 2011; Orr et
61 al., 2017).

62 Ocean BGC models in ESMs have been demonstrated to have large uncertainties, em-
63 phasizing their need for improvement. Their accuracy is hampered by various sources of
64 errors, which are dominated by errors in the physical model and the sub-optimally tuned
65 empirical parameterizations of the biogeochemical dynamics (Doney et al., 2004). The
66 resolution of ESMs contributing to the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project version 6
67 (CMIP6; O'Neill et al., 2016) are too coarse to explicitly resolve the most important physical
68 processes. This limitation introduces significant uncertainties in key processes that influence
69 ocean BGC, such as eddies, upwelling, and winter mixing. In addition to physical model
70 uncertainties, the BGC model itself uses numerous poorly known parameters to describe
71 the complex biogeochemical process (Kriest et al., 2010; Löptien & Dietze, 2017), such as
72 the growth of phytoplankton and the grazing rate by zooplankton. These parameters are
73 often obtained from laboratory experiments conducted on individual species. They are then
74 typically extrapolated and applied as globally uniform constants in BGC models (Oschlies,
75 2006). This approach can be sub-optimal considering the spatially and temporally diverse
76 environmental conditions simulated across the different ocean regions.

77 Manual tuning of these parameters is complicated and time-consuming, and it has
78 become increasingly cumbersome with the increasing complexity of models. A classical ap-
79 proach to tuning BGC model parameters is to first assess the model sensitivity to parameters
80 in isolation and manually tune them in forced configuration (with atmospheric boundary
81 conditions prescribed). Some of these parameters need to be re-tuned when transitioning
82 from a forced to a coupled configuration, as the non-linear interactions via the coupling can
83 influence the variability of the individual component and can amplify biases (e.g., Koseki
84 et al., 2018). It requires substantial computational resources due to one by one tuning

85 of the parameters, and sometimes subjective decisions by model developers. Furthermore,
86 many non-linear physical, chemical, and biological processes can simultaneously influence
87 the marine ecosystem, making it challenging to isolate the impact of individual biogeo-
88 chemical parameters on the overall system (there is a non-unique solution). For example,
89 phytoplankton growth and zooplankton grazing rates can both affect the phytoplankton
90 concentration. There is a need for a non-subjective method that can efficiently estimate
91 model BGC parameters and isolate the role of the parameter sensitivity within ESMs based
92 on all available data. We explore the potential of using data assimilation (DA) to build an
93 efficient framework to optimize BGC parameters and improve the model's accuracy.

94 DA provides a statistical framework to estimate the most accurate model states (and/or
95 parameters) based on a set of observations, a prior model estimate, and statistical informa-
96 tion on their uncertainties. DA has been instrumental in the progress of numerical weather
97 predictions (Bauer et al., 2015) as well as other fields in geosciences (Carrassi et al., 2018).
98 The Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF; Evensen, 1994) is a state-of-the-art DA method that
99 relies on an ensemble of model realizations (a Monte Carlo forward model integration) to
100 estimate the forecast error covariance – used to quantify the forecast error and the multivari-
101 ate relationship. The EnKF was also shown to provide an efficient framework to estimate
102 model parameters (Anderson, 2001; Annan et al., 2005; Evensen, 2009; Massonnet et al.,
103 2014), which is the focus of our study. Model parameters are perturbed jointly for each
104 ensemble member and added to the state vector during the assimilation process (by state
105 augmentation). The multiple parameters are estimated simultaneously (unlike one by one
106 in the manual tuning) based on their covariance with the observed variables. DA finds the
107 optimal parameter likelihood that minimizes the discrepancies of the model with respect
108 to the observations, considering their relative uncertainties. Parameter estimation using an
109 EnKF has been successfully applied in several BGC models (Simon et al., 2012; Simon &
110 Bertino, 2012; Simon et al., 2015; Gharamti, Samuelsen, et al., 2017; Gharamti, Tjiputra,
111 et al., 2017; Singh et al., 2022; Mammun et al., 2022) with varying levels of complexity in
112 the DA, the model, and the framework.

113 Singh et al. (2022) tested BGC parameter estimation (PE) in an idealized perfect (or
114 identical) twin experiment framework (Halem & Dlouhy, 1984), where artificial observations
115 are constructed from a simulation of the same model for which the parameters are perturbed.
116 A twin experiment is convenient because the state of the truth (as well as the true parameter
117 values if perturbed) is known. Conversely, in a real framework (i.e., when real observations
118 are assimilated), the sources of errors and the uncertainty are multiple, e.g., errors from
119 the other components (e.g., ocean physics) or from BGC parameters not considered in the
120 parameter estimation. Sparse and noisy observations for the BGC component pose another

121 challenge (Löptien & Dietze, 2015) and most attempts to perform parameter estimation in
122 the real framework have shown strong limitations (Kane et al., 2011; Simon et al., 2015;
123 Mammun et al., 2022).

124 A key challenge when estimating parameters with ESMs is that bias from the other
125 components can influence the parameter estimation process (Sinha et al., 2010; Dietze &
126 Löptien, 2013; Löptien & Dietze, 2019). As a result, the BGC parameters can be tuned
127 to compensate for biases originating from the ocean physical model. Löptien and Dietze
128 (2019) illustrated the consequences of such bias compensation with an idealized framework.
129 In their study, while estimating BGC parameters could drastically reduce errors during
130 the estimation period, it introduces large deviations in climate projections under anthro-
131 pogenic forcing - e.g., in total oceanic carbon content and suboxic volume. To mitigate the
132 compensating bias issue, we propose to estimate BGC model parameters while applying a
133 state constraint on the ocean physics, thereby reducing the risk of bias compensation during
134 parameter estimation.

135 While most parameters are considered global, there is evidence that parameter values
136 should be able to vary spatially (J. F. Tjiputra, 2007; Simon et al., 2015; Gharamti, Tjiputra,
137 et al., 2017; Mammun et al., 2022). For example, Gharamti, Tjiputra, et al. (2017) estimated
138 the BGC parameters of a single-column model with an EnKF at three stations spread around
139 the world where the physical and BGC state are continuously monitored. They found that
140 the parameters estimated for the different stations differ substantially, which exhibits the
141 complex interactions between multiple parameters and the environments. Singh et al. (2022)
142 show that spatially varying parameters can be successfully retrieved by DA within an ESM
143 in an idealized framework, even with a sparse climatology observational network that mimics
144 the real one.

145 This study builds on Gharamti, Tjiputra, et al. (2017) and Singh et al. (2022) that
146 successfully used the dual-one-step-ahead-smoother (DOSA) iterative methods to optimize
147 BGC parameters. Specifically, this work advances the approach of Singh et al. (2022), which
148 successfully demonstrated the method within a fully coupled Earth System Model (ESM),
149 but this time by utilizing a real framework where real-world observations are assimilated in-
150 stead of artificial observations. Before doing the parameter estimations, we assess the impact
151 of reducing the physical ocean model bias on the BGC performance within the Norwegian
152 Earth System Model. For the parameter estimation in the real framework, the original
153 DOSA scheme was unsuccessful for reasons detailed in the manuscript, with parameters ex-
154 ceeding realistic ranges and reanalysis (i.e., a model reconstruction with state constraints)
155 with the estimated parameter showing a deterioration compared to that performed with
156 the default parameters. A revised framework is proposed based on the iterative ensemble

157 smoother (IES) method (Evensen, 2018). The BGC parameters are estimated using the
 158 BGC state error (i.e., mismatch with observations) of a coupled reanalysis that assimilates
 159 climatological-mean observations of the ocean physical state. The reanalysis is produced
 160 by using the EnKF state estimation of ocean physical state variables. Globally uniform
 161 and spatially varying parameters are compared, and we assess the benefit of using multiple
 162 iterations. Finally, we verify the method for a long coupled reanalysis, which constrains the
 163 ocean physical state with time-varying observations.

164 The subsequent sections of this paper are structured as follows. Section 2 provides an
 165 overview of the ESM used, the ocean physics state constraint scheme (Section 2.2), and
 166 the parameter estimation algorithms (Section 2.3). We then introduce the observations
 167 (Section 3), the experimental design (Section 4), and the validation metrics (Section 5).
 168 Section 6 presents and discusses the results: *i*) how reducing error in the ocean physics
 169 (Section 6.1) impacts the BGC state *ii*) discussing the BGC parameters with the global and
 170 spatial approach (Section 6.2) *iii*) showing the impact of the parameter on the BGC state
 171 in a re-run (Section 6.3) *iv*) assessing the potential of using several iterations (Section 6.4)
 172 and *v*) verifying the estimated parameter on the performance of a long reanalysis (Section
 173 6.5). The concluding remarks of this work are outlined in Section 7.

174 **2 Norwegian Climate Prediction Model for state constraint and param-** 175 **eter estimation**

176 The Norwegian Climate Prediction Model (NorCPM) combines the Norwegian Earth
 177 System Model (NorESM; e.g., Bentsen et al., 2013) and a suite of DA solutions based
 178 on the EnKF (Evensen, 2003). NorCPM is typically used to provide coupled reanalysis
 179 (Counillon et al., 2016) and seasonal-to-decadal climate prediction (Kimmritz et al., 2019;
 180 Wang et al., 2019; Bethke et al., 2021). Here we use NorCPM1, which contributed to the
 181 Decadal Climate Prediction Project (DCPP) of the CMIP6 Project (Bethke et al., 2021)
 182 and contributes yearly to the World Meteorological Organisation “lead centre for operational
 183 annual-to-decadal prediction” (Hermanson et al., 2022). Here, we explore how DA can be
 184 used to optimize model parameters. The error in the ocean physics state is also constrained
 185 using DA to reduce error at the boundary condition of the BGC component. The parameter
 186 estimation method involves the two recursive steps: (i) producing an ensemble of coupled
 187 BGC reanalyses, where the BGC parameters are perturbed, and the physical ocean state
 188 is constrained towards observed climatology using DA (Section 2.2) and (ii) estimating the
 189 BGC parameters based on the monthly climatological error of the reanalysis (Section 2.3).

2.1 The Norwegian Earth System Model

NorCPM1 was built on the NorESM version 1 configured at a medium resolution (NorESM1-ME; Bentsen et al., 2013; J. Tjiputra et al., 2013), which uses CMIP6 forcing, and includes a bug fix in the atmospheric chemistry and was further re-calibrated (Bethke et al., 2021). The model is based on the Community Earth System Model (CESM1.0.4; Hurrell et al., 2013), but with modified aerosol chemistry in the atmosphere and the ocean component is replaced with an isopycnal coordinate ocean general circulation model. Specifically, the NorESM1 atmospheric component is from the modified version of the Community Atmosphere Model (CAM4-OSLO; Kirkevåg et al., 2013). CAM4-OSLO replaces the original prescribed aerosol formulation of the Community Atmosphere Model (CAM4; Neale et al., 2010) with a prognostic aerosol life cycle formulation using emissions and new aerosol-cloud interaction schemes (Kirkevåg et al., 2013). The ocean physical component of NorESM1 (Called BLOM for “Bergen layered Ocean Model”) is built from the Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model (MICOM; Bleck & Smith, 1990; Bleck et al., 1992) with modified numerics and physics (Bentsen et al., 2013). The vertical density coordinate of the ocean component minimizes spurious diapycnal mixing, improving the conservation and transformation of tracers and water masses. The ocean carbon cycle model is based on the Hamburg Ocean Carbon Cycle (HAMOCC5.1; Maier-Reimer et al., 2005). The other components, Community Land Model (CLM4; Oleson et al., 2010; Lawrence et al., 2011) and sea ice model (CICE4; Gent et al., 2011; Holland et al., 2012) are adopted in their original form from CESM1.

The atmospheric component CAM4 and the land component CLM4 are configured on an approximately 2° finite volume grid, with horizontal resolutions of 1.9° in latitude and 2.5° in longitude. The ocean model BLOM and the sea ice model CICE4 have a horizontal resolution of about $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$. BLOM features 51 isopycnal layers plus 2 additional layers for the bulk mixed layer, with time-evolving thicknesses and densities. The ocean BGC component HAMOCC uses the same spatial and temporal resolution as BLOM.

The HAMOCC marine ecosystem module, which is the focus of this study, is based on an NPZD-type (Nutrients-Phytoplankton-Zooplankton-Detritus) ecosystem model (Six & Maier-Reimer, 1996; J. Tjiputra et al., 2010). At the euphotic layer (i.e., top 100 m), the model simulates primary productivity driven by phytoplankton growth, which is limited by temperature, light availability, in addition to multi-nutrient co-limitation of phosphate, nitrate and dissolved iron. Consumed surface nutrients are assimilated into phytoplankton soft tissue. A fraction of the phytoplankton mass is eventually turned into dissolved and particulate organic matters (DOM and POM) through a chain of processes such as zooplankton grazing, phytoplankton exudation, zooplankton excretion, and mortality. A single species

226 of DOM is implemented and advected by the ocean circulation, while POM primarily sinks
 227 into the ocean interior. POM and DOM are remineralized to inorganic nutrients, given suf-
 228 ficient oxygen concentration, at constant remineralization rates. In this version of NorESM,
 229 the BGC component does not provide any feedback to the ocean physics component.

230 The HAMOCC model in NorCPM1 incorporates a range of parameters to simulate the
 231 biogeochemical characteristics of the ocean, with a comprehensive list provided by Maier-
 232 Reimer et al. (2005). In this study, our primary objective is to optimize a selection of five
 233 parameters chosen explicitly for their influences on the carbon cycle and with connections
 234 to the assimilated BGC observations. These parameters include

- 235 1. the half-saturation constant for nutrient uptake during phytoplankton growth (K_N),
- 236 2. the maximum zooplankton grazing rate (G_{max}),
- 237 3. the sinking speed for particulate organic carbon (W_{poc}),
- 238 4. the half-saturation constant for silicate uptake during biogenic opal production (K_{Si}),
- 239 5. the remineralization rate of particulate organic carbon (R_{poc}).

240 The parameters are listed in Table 1 Column-1. In the HAMOCC model source codes, the
 241 parameter's acronyms for K_N , G_{max} , W_{poc} , K_{Si} , and R_{poc} are referred to as *bkphy*, *grazra*,
 242 *wpoc*, *bkopal* and *drempoc*, respectively, which can be used to facilitate straightforward
 243 tracking in the codes.

244 The above parameters affect the distributions of nutrients (N), phytoplankton (P),
 245 zooplankton (Z), and organic matters (OM) in the water column, as illustrated in the
 246 following equations.

$$\frac{\partial N}{\partial t} = Adv(N) - f(T, L) \cdot \frac{N}{N + K_N} \cdot P + f_{remin}(POM, DOM) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial t} = Adv(P) + f(T, L) \cdot \frac{N}{N + K_N} \cdot P - G_{max} \cdot \frac{P - P_{min}}{P + K_P} \cdot Z - f_{loss}(P) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial POM}{\partial t} = Adv(POM) - R_{poc} \cdot POM + f_z(W_{poc}, POM) \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial diatoms}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial P}{\partial t} \cdot \frac{Si}{Si + K_{Si}}, \quad (4)$$

247 where $f(T, L)$ represents the function of temperature (T) and light (L), POM is particulate
 248 organic matters, DOM is dissolved organic matters, K_P is phytoplankton half-saturation
 249 constant for zooplankton grazing, P_{min} is minimum phytoplankton concentration and Si
 250 represents silicate concentration.

251 Nutrients are governed by physical circulation (*Adv*), phytoplankton growth rate as
 252 a function of light and temperature, and remineralizations of particulate and dissolved
 253 organic matters (Equation 1). In addition to advection and growth rate, phytoplankton
 254 is grazed by zooplankton and loss to mortality and exudation (Equation 2). Particulate
 255 organic matters are advected, remineralized and exported vertically into depth (Equation
 256 3). Finally, diatom production is implicitly parameterized as a function of phytoplankton
 257 and silicate concentration (Equation 4). A comprehensive description of the ecosystem
 258 formulation in HAMOCC is available in J. F. Tjiputra (2007).

259 For more details of other components of NorCPM1, including their overall performance,
 260 the reader is referred to Bethke et al. (2021).

Table 1. Description of parameters (Column 1) along with their default values and initial ensemble spread (or prior spread) in parentheses (Column 2). The estimated global BGC parameter values from Iteration 1 and Iteration 2 are presented in Column 3 and Column 4, respectively.

Parameter description (acronym) [<i>unit</i>]	Default values (initial ensemble std.)	Global estimated ensemble mean	
		Iteration-1	Iteration-2
1. The half-saturation constant for nutrient uptake during phytoplankton growth (K_N) [$mmol\ P\ m^{-3}$]	2.0×10^{-7} (0.66×10^{-7})	1.02×10^{-7}	0.60×10^{-7}
2. The maximum zooplankton grazing rate (G_{max}) [day^{-1}]	1.0 (0.33)	1.13	1.27
3. The half-saturation constant for silicate uptake during biogenic opal production (K_{Si}) [$mmol\ Si\ m^{-3}$]	1.5×10^{-6} (0.50×10^{-6})	2.52×10^{-6}	3.30×10^{-6}
4. The sinking speed for particulate organic carbon (W_{poc}) [day^{-1}]	5.0 (1.66)	6.0	6.5
5. The remineralization rate of particulate organic carbon (R_{poc}) [day^{-1}]	3.0×10^{-2} (1.0×10^{-2})	0.90×10^{-2}	0.91×10^{-2}

261 2.2 State constraint on the ocean physics

262 This study employs the dual one-step ahead iterative smoothing ensemble scheme
 263 (DOSA-EnKF, Gharamti et al., 2015; Gharamti, Tjiputra, et al., 2017) for sustaining error
 264 in the ocean physics to a low level. The DOSA-EnKF is an ensemble data assimilation technique that uses a dual iteration step, where the state variables undergo both a smoothing and an analysis step. We use DOSA-EnKF based on the deterministic EnKF DA algorithm (DEnKF; Sakov & Oke, 2008); a square-root version of the EnKF. We do not describe the equations of the DOSA-EnKF, which are detailed in Singh et al. (2022).
 268

269 The assimilation cycle is monthly, and we update the full ocean physics state vector
 270 (Counillon et al., 2016). The adjustment of the other compartments (e.g., atmosphere and sea ice) occurs dynamically in between the monthly assimilation cycle. The model state vector is constructed in isopycnal coordinates and includes temperature, salinity, layer thickness and velocities of the entire water column (53 layers, see Counillon et al., 2014;
 273

274 Wang et al., 2017). We use the upscaling super layer algorithm developed by Wang et
275 al. (2016) to update layer thickness, which prevents the analysis from returning negative
276 quantities and preserves heat, mass and salt.

277 We assimilate the monthly average observations in the middle of the month and update
278 the instantaneous model state. Assimilation of monthly data implies that the innovation
279 (i.e., observations minus model state) compares the variability of an instantaneous model
280 snapshot with that of monthly averaged observations. An alternative has been investigated,
281 where data were assimilated at the end of the month; thus, the monthly model averaged
282 output was compared with the monthly averaged observations. However, the latter approach
283 shows poorer performance for reanalysis and no improvements during prediction (Billeau
284 et al., 2016). This suggests that comparing model snapshots with monthly data is not an
285 important distinction for our system.

286 Our ocean data assimilation (ODA) yields an update of the BGC mass component
287 because we assimilate in isopycnal coordinates – i.e. we update the layer thickness. The
288 upscaling method (Wang et al., 2016) ensures that mass and tracers are preserved by as-
289 similation. Bethke et al. (2021) demonstrated that our ODA approach does not introduce a
290 spurious impact on ocean BGC in a coupled reanalysis covering the period 1950–2020, pro-
291 duced for CMIP6 DCP. They analyzed the impact of the ODA with anomaly assimilation
292 (i.e., without changing the ocean mean state) on the BGC mean state. The deviation of the
293 mean BGC state relates to the modulation of internal variability, and it remains well within
294 the possible mean state found in a large ensemble of historical ensembles. This verifies that
295 our ODA implementation does not introduce spurious upwelling at the Equator, an artefact
296 often found with ODA (While et al., 2010; Park et al., 2018).

297 The remaining assimilation configurations are set as in Bethke et al. (2021). Assimi-
298 lation is done in a local analysis framework (Sakov et al., 2012). A latitude-varying quasi-
299 Gaussian localization function (Gaspari & Cohn, 1999) is used to smooth the assimilation
300 impact at the boundary of the localization radius. The localization radius has a bimodal
301 Gaussian function that varies with latitude. At the Equator, the radius has a local minimum
302 of 1500 km, where covariances become anisotropic. In the mid-latitudes, the radius reaches
303 a maximum of 2300 km. There is another minimum in the high latitudes, where the Rossby
304 radius is small (Wang et al., 2017). We use the moderation and a pre-screening technique
305 (Sakov et al., 2012) to sustain the ensemble spread during the assimilation.

2.3 Iterative ensemble smoother for offline parameter estimation

The online parameter estimation tested in Singh et al. (2022) was performed in a twin-experiment setup (i.e., idealized framework) within NorCPM1. An ensemble with perturbed parameters is run forward, and the parameter likelihood is updated monthly by augmenting the parameters with the state vector during the EnKF update. We tested this approach in a real framework (i.e. using real observations), but it was unsuccessful – parameters reached unrealistic values, and model performance was poorer than with default parameter values. Unlike in the idealized framework where the model errors are, by construction, only coming from the model parameter, the model errors in a real system could also originate from the other components (e.g., ocean physics) or from BGC parameters not considered in the parameter estimation. We suspect that the error inherited from the ocean grew faster than that of the BGC parameter, which confuses the relation between the parameter values and the model-data misfit. Furthermore, it was challenging to sustain a consistent ensemble spread level as several of the hypotheses of DA are not satisfied — our DA assumes the model is perfect (with the exception of the parameters being perturbed) and the error to be Gaussian distributed, neither of which are satisfied. As a consequence, the ensemble spread collapsed rapidly even with an adaptive inflation scheme (unless unrealistic inflation factors were used). This is problematic because, with ensemble DA, the ensemble spread quantifies the amplitude of the corrections. Consequently, it gave more weight to the bloom occurring early in our simulation, and the parameter estimation converged to different solutions depending on when the experiment was started (e.g., in winter or summer). While we do not present results from this method here, as it is beyond the scope of this paper, it served as the foundation for revising the method for application to the real system.

We revised our approach and used an iterative ensemble smoother (IES, Evensen, 2018) that proceeds as follows. First, a coupled reanalysis with ocean physical state constraint (Section 2.2) is run with each ensemble member using a set of perturbed BGC parameter values. Second, a single analysis updates the ensemble of BGC parameters based on the misfit between the BGC state from the reanalysis and from the BGC observations. We refer to this approach as 'offline' because the parameter estimation is conducted a-posteriori; i.e., after the coupled reanalysis has been produced (no parameter estimation is performed during the coupled reanalysis run). Several iterations can be applied, and in this case, the reanalysis starts from the ensemble of estimated parameters from the previous iteration.

The IES scheme nicely handles the challenges met with the online DOSA scheme. First, as we continuously assimilate the ocean physics state with the DOSA scheme (Section 2.2), the errors inherited from the ocean physics are kept to a low level, and errors related to the BGC parameters can grow and play a more significant role in the overall error term. Second,

342 as the assimilation considers all calendar months jointly, there is no longer preferential
 343 influence related to the start of the cycle, unlike when we use the online parameter estimation
 344 of (Singh et al., 2022).

345 The BGC parameter estimation with the IES is fed on BGC monthly outputs of a
 346 coupled reanalysis that assimilates the monthly climatology of ocean physics. This removes
 347 interannual variability in the ocean and makes it easier to relate the BGC error (i.e., dis-
 348 crepancies between modeled and observed BGC) to the BGC parameter values. However, as
 349 the same climatology observations are repeatedly assimilated every year, we cannot consider
 350 the successive yearly cycles as independent. It takes about 10 years for the BGC parameter
 351 sensitivity to emerge and dominate the signal. Therefore, we first perform a 10-year spin-up
 352 with perturbed parameters (NorESM_PP), followed by a 3-year reanalysis (REANA_PP)
 353 assimilating monthly temperature and salinity climatology (Table 3 and Section 4). We
 354 perform the offline parameter estimation only on the last yearly cycle of the reanalysis (i.e.,
 355 the year 2017) after the ocean physics has reached stable performance (Figure 1).

We implement the offline parameter estimation using the DEnKF DA algorithm. The following is a mathematical description of the parameter estimation scheme:

The ensemble of initial model parameters is denoted $\boldsymbol{\theta}^i \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times m}$ – i.e., the ensemble of parameters before the estimation step with p being the number of parameters and m being the ensemble size. $\boldsymbol{\theta}^e \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times m}$ is the resulting estimated parameter ensemble. The ensemble mean of the parameter $\overline{\boldsymbol{\theta}^e} \in \mathbb{R}^p$ and the parameter ensemble anomaly $\mathbf{A}_\theta^e \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times m}$ are estimated as follows:

$$\overline{\boldsymbol{\theta}^e} = \overline{\boldsymbol{\theta}^i} + \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{y}_{1:L} - H\overline{\mathbf{X}_{1:L}^a}), \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{A}_\theta^e = \mathbf{A}_\theta^i - \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{KHA}_{1:L}^a, \quad (6)$$

356 where $\mathbf{X}_{1:L}^a = [\mathbf{x}_1^a, \mathbf{x}_2^a, \dots, \mathbf{x}_m^a] \in \mathbb{R}^{nL \times m}$ represents the ensemble of BGC state vectors.
 357 Each ensemble member, $\mathbf{x}_i^a \in \mathbb{R}^{nL}$, is a concatenation of the corresponding reanalysis mem-
 358 ber over the last L months (here, reanalysis ensemble was produced with constrained ocean
 359 physics and DOSA scheme, see Section 2.2). Superscript a represents the analysis state
 360 from ocean physics assimilation, n is the dimension of the state vector at a single time
 361 step. Here we use the monthly averaged data over one year, i.e., $L = 12$. $\overline{\mathbf{X}_{1:L}^a} \in \mathbb{R}^{nL}$
 362 and $\mathbf{A}_{1:L}^a \in \mathbb{R}^{nL \times m}$ are the ensemble mean and anomaly of $\mathbf{X}_{1:L}^a$. Similarly, we denote the
 363 observations $\mathbf{y}_{1:L} \in \mathbb{R}^o$, the concatenated time records at a comparable time to $\mathbf{X}_{1:L}^a$, with
 364 o being the total number of observations aggregated over L records (the monthly climato-
 365 logical BGC observations). The observation operator H interpolates the model fields (here,

366 the monthly BGC state) to the observation space bi-linearly and \mathbf{H} is its tangent linear
 367 operator. The Kalman gain \mathbf{K} is calculated as follows:

$$\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{A}_\theta^i (\mathbf{A}_{1:L}^a)^T \mathbf{H}^T \left(\mathbf{H} \mathbf{A}_{1:L}^a (\mathbf{A}_{1:L}^a)^T \mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{R} \right)^{-1}, \quad (7)$$

368 where $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{R}^{o \times o}$ is the observation error covariance, assumed to be diagonal (observation er-
 369 ror assumed to be uncorrelated) and with the observation error variance defined as described
 370 in Section 3. The superscript \mathbf{T} denotes the matrix transpose.

The estimated parameter ensemble θ^e can be reconstructed as:

$$\theta^e = \bar{\theta}^e + \mathbf{A}_\theta^e \quad (8)$$

371 For the second iteration, a new reanalysis is rerun from the same initial state as the first
 372 iteration but with the parameter values estimated from the previous iteration. Consequently,
 373 we can iterate Equations 5 and 6, utilizing the updated ensemble mean $\overline{\mathbf{X}_{1:L}^a}$ and anomaly
 374 $\mathbf{A}_{1:L}^a$, both of which are derived from the coupled reanalysis of the second iteration. The
 375 observation error should be multiplied by the number of iterations one intends to perform
 376 (Evensen, 2018) – to prevent over-assimilation. For linear systems, using multiple iterations
 377 (with multiplied observation error variance) coincides with a single iteration update. How-
 378 ever, using multiple iterations provides superior performance for non-linear cases (Evensen,
 379 2018) as it can better handle the non-linear response to the model parameters.

380 The approach is tested for estimating global and spatially varying BGC parameters. In
 381 global parameter estimation, the model parameters are a vector ($\in \mathbb{R}^p$) and are estimated
 382 based on the innovation from the entire domain. For spatially varying parameters, the
 383 parameters are estimated for each horizontal model grid point, but the same value is used
 384 vertically in the model integration. The parameters are estimated with a local analysis
 385 framework (Evensen, 2003), i.e., updating the parameter value of each grid cell based on
 386 local observations within a localization radius. The radius varies with latitude, as explained
 387 in Section 2.2. However, the BGC climatology observations that were assimilated are heavily
 388 correlated in space (i.e., \mathbf{R} is not diagonal in Equation 7). Therefore, we have only retained
 389 the four nearest observation profiles of each observation type to avoid over-assimilation. See
 390 Section 3 for details on the observations.

391 **3 Observations**

392 We use two distinct sets of global observations for DA: (1) ocean physics monthly cli-
 393 matology for state constraints and (2) BGC monthly climatology for parameter estimation,

394 both from the World Ocean Atlas 2018 release (WOA18) datasets (Locarnini et al., 2018;
395 Zweng et al., 2019; Garcia et al., 2019a, 2019b). The ocean physics estimate consists of
396 temperature and salinity (TS), and the BGC includes nutrients (PO_4 ; phosphate and NO_3 ;
397 nitrate) and oxygen (O_2). Nutrients extend down to 800 m depth, whereas temperature,
398 salinity and oxygen profiles are available down to 1500 m deep. To estimate the observation
399 error needed for the assimilation, we use the quadratic sum of the error estimate from the
400 WOA18 dataset and add one de-seasoned (with the climatological-mean seasonal cycle re-
401 moved) standard deviation in time from our model computed over 1980-2010 to account for
402 representation error (Janjić et al., 2018). The observation errors are estimated at each grid
403 cell and for each calendar month.

404 The WOA18 climatological estimates are available on a regular horizontal grid with a
405 spatial resolution of $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$. These gridded datasets are generated through objective analysis,
406 which involves interpolating and extrapolating data from individual measurement points to
407 create a continuous gridded product. While the ocean physics climatological estimate is quite
408 accurate overall (Locarnini et al., 2018; Zweng et al., 2019), the situation differs for BGC
409 data. BGC measurements are sparse and heterogeneously distributed in space and time.
410 Therefore, for BGC, we only use the estimate where at least one measurement is available
411 within the corresponding grid-square area. Ocean physics observations in ice-covered regions
412 are excluded. The sea ice mask is estimated using the 30-year climatological mean sea ice
413 data from the NorESM historical model simulation (1980-2010). BGC measurements located
414 closer than 4 model grid points from the sea ice mask are excluded.

415 The validation of parameter estimation results includes additional observations not
416 used during the parameter estimation process. It consists of silicate (Si), dissolved inorganic
417 carbon (DIC), total alkalinity (TA), primary production (PP) and sea-air CO_2 fluxes. These
418 observations, referred to as independent data, play a crucial role in assessing the impact of
419 parameter estimation methods.

420 In this study we also assimilated time-varying observations of sea surface temperature
421 (SST) from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) Optimum In-
422 terpolation SST version 2 (Reynolds et al., 2002), and subsurface ocean temperature and
423 salinity hydrographic profile observations from the EN4 dataset (EN4.2.2; Gouretski & Re-
424 seghetti, 2010) to create a 30 years reanalysis. The aim was to assess the performance of
425 estimated parameters with time-varying ocean physics. We used the SST observation errors
426 provided by NOAA and the hydrographic profile observation errors estimated by Wang et
427 al. (2017). Both SST and hydrographic observation errors vary in space and time.

428 A summary of observations utilized for parameter estimation and validation is provided
 429 in Table 2.

Table 2. List of observations utilized (Column-1), with the second column detailing the data type; whether time-varying or climatology. The reference period for the latter type is provided in the third Column. The second-to-last column signifies if data is assimilated (in ODA or PE), while the last column contains the observational reference.

Observation variables	data type	Clim. Period	Remark	References
Temperature	climatology	2005–2017	Assimilated (ODA)	WOA 2018 (Locarnini et al., 2018)
Salinity	climatology	2005–2017	Assimilated (ODA)	WOA 2018 (Zweng et al., 2019)
Oxygen	climatology	1960–2018	Assimilated (PE)	WOA 2018 (Garcia et al., 2019a)
Phosphate	climatology	1960–2018	Assimilated (PE)	WOA 2018 (Garcia et al., 2019b)
Nitrate	climatology	1960–2018	Assimilated (PE)	WOA 2018 (Garcia et al., 2019b)
Silicate	climatology	1960–2018	Independent	WOA 2018 (Garcia et al., 2019b)
Dissolved Inorganic Carbon	climatology	2004–2017	Independent	Kepler et al. (2020)
Total Alkalinity	climatology	1972–2017	Independent	Broullón et al. (2019)
Sea–air CO ₂ fluxes	climatology	1982–2015	Independent	Landschützer et al. (2017)
Net primary production	climatology	2003–2012	Independent	Average of the three remote sensing products (VGPM, Eppley-VGPM, and CbPM) from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (Behrenfeld & Falkowski, 1997; Westberry et al., 2008)
Sea Surface Temperature	Time-varying	–	Assimilated (ODA)	NOAA OI SST version2 (Reynolds et al., 2002)
Temperature	Time-varying	–	Assimilated (ODA)	EN4.2.2 (Gouretski & Reseghetti, 2010)
Salinity	Time-varying	–	Assimilated (ODA)	EN4.2.2 (Gouretski & Reseghetti, 2010)

430 4 Experimental design

431 We now describe the series of experiments that we have used to estimate parameters
 432 and assess their performance. Each experiment uses a 30-member ensemble run and is
 433 outlined as follows:

- 434 • **NorESM_DP** – an ensemble of historical runs with default parameters (DP). It
 435 serves as a benchmark to assess the baseline performance of the default version of
 436 NorESM that contributed to CMIP6. The initial ensemble was produced by selecting
 437 30 random model states from a stable pre-industrial run. The ensemble is integrated
 438 from 1850 until 2014 with CMIP6 historical forcing, and extended with the Shared
 439 Socioeconomic Pathway (SSP) 2-4.5 scenario forcing from 2015 to 2026 (Bethke et
 440 al., 2021).
- 441 • **REANA_DP** – a coupled reanalysis using DP and ocean physics assimilation of
 442 monthly climatology of temperature and salinity repeated each year (Section 2.2).
 443 The reanalysis is branched from NorESM_DP and runs from 2015 until 2026. It helps
 444 to estimate how the BGC model responds to reducing bias in ocean physics.

- 445 • **NorESM_PP** – an ensemble of simulations (as NorESM_DP) utilizing perturbed
446 BGC parameters (PP). The simulation was branched from NorESM_DP in January
447 2005 and ran until January 2015. The 30-member ensemble perturbs all five param-
448 eters simultaneously by adding Gaussian perturbations to the default values – with the
449 standard deviation set at 33% (Table 1). We enforce that parameters remain within
450 the range 60% to 200% of the default values.
- 451 • **REANA_PP** – a reanalysis (as REANA_DP), but run with perturbed BGC param-
452 eters and initialized from NorESM_PP. The mismatch of the REANA_PP reanalysis
453 data with observed BGC climatology for 2017 is used to estimate the parameters
454 in the first iteration (Iteration-1, Section 2.3). The estimated parameter values are
455 discussed and presented in Section 6.2.
- 456 • **REANA_GP** – a reanalysis (as REANA_PP) with global estimated parameters ob-
457 tained from Iteration-1. The performance of the REANA_GP is assessed to inves-
458 tigate the benefit of global parameter estimation (Section 6.3). The mismatch of
459 REANA_GP with observed BGC climatology is used to estimate the global param-
460 eters of the second iteration (Iteration-2, Section 6.2).
- 461 • **REANA_SP** – a reanalysis (as REANA_GP), but with spatial estimated parameters
462 from Iteration-1 (Section 6.2). This experiment is conducted to evaluate the perfor-
463 mance of spatially varying estimated parameter values and to investigate if there is
464 any benefit over the global one (Section 6.3).
- 465 • **REANA_GP2** – a reanalysis same as REANA_GP, but with global estimated pa-
466 rameters taken from Iteration-2. This experiment helps to investigate the benefit of
467 the multi-iteration approach for parameter estimation (Section 6.4).
- 468 • **REANA_IAV_GP2** – a long reanalysis generated using assimilation of time-varying
469 ocean physics observations- i.e., including interannual variability (IAV). It runs from
470 1985 to 2022, with the global parameter estimated in REANA_GP2. It assimilates
471 time-varying observation of SST and TS profiles at a monthly cycle. The initial state
472 was branched from NorESM_DP in 1982. For REANA_IAV_GP2, the first eight years
473 of the reanalysis (1985-1992) are discarded (considered as a spinup to adjust to the
474 new parameters), and the remaining 30 years (1993-2022) are used for validation
475 (Section 6.5).

476 All the experiments with names starting with REANA imply they are assimilating ocean
477 physics to sustain its error at a low level. A summary of the experiments is given in Table
478 3.

Table 3. List of experiments.

Experiment Name	Observations (if assimilated)	Starting initial ensemble	Parameters used	Time period	Description
NorESM_DP	-	Pre-industrial	Default parameters	1850 - 2026	Baseline
REANA_DP	TS clim.	NorESM_DP	Default parameters	2015 - 2026	Reanalysis to evaluate the impact of reduced ocean physics bias on BGC
NorESM_PP	-	NorESM_DP	Perturbed parameters	2005 - 2015	Spin-up run for PP.
REANA_PP	TS clim.	NorESM_PP	Perturbed parameters	2015 - 2017	Reanalysis input data to perform first iteration PE
REANA_GP	TS clim.	NorESM_PP	Global estimated parameters from Iteration-1	2015 - 2026	Reanalysis to evaluate the first iteration global PE and also input data to perform the second iteration
REANA_SP	TS clim.	NorESM_PP	Spatial estimated parameters from Iteration-1	2015 - 2026	Reanalysis to evaluate if any benefit of spatial PE over global one
REANA_GP2	TS clim.	NorESM_PP	Global estimated parameters from Iteration-2	2015 - 2026	Reanalysis to evaluate benefit of second iteration global PE
REANA_IJV_GP2	TS time-varying	NorESM_DP	Global estimated parameters from Iteration-2	1985 - 2022	Reanalysis to evaluate second iteration global PE with interannually varying ocean forcings.

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5 Validation Metrics

The performance of the numerical experiments is analyzed based on the following metrics:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N W_i (\bar{x}_i^f - y_i)^2}, \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Bias} = \sum_{i=1}^N W_i (\bar{x}_i^f - y_i), \quad (10)$$

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where RMSE denotes the area-weighted root mean square error, with W_i being the weight for normalizing the grid cell area and N being the total number of data used in the validation. \bar{x}_i^f denotes the model ensemble mean corresponding to the i^{th} observation, while y_i is the i^{th} observed values. We perform bi-linear interpolation of the observations to the model grid. The values of N and W_i can vary depending on the context. For point-wise RMSE and bias calculations, there is no area normalization (i.e., $W_i=1/N$) and N is the number of timesteps. For the global RMSE and bias error, N is the total number of model

487 grid cells, and W_i is the area of the i^{th} cell divided by the sum of the total grid cell area.
 488 The RMSE and bias profiles are the time average of the global error.

489 6 Results and Discussions

490 6.1 Impact of reduced ocean physics bias on BGC

491 The accuracy of the underlying ocean physics strongly influences the accuracy of BGC
 492 simulations. Reducing the ocean physics bias is expected to improve the performance of BGC
 493 simulations. However, the performance of BGC simulations can also be negatively impacted
 494 by inaccurate parameters, which may have been tuned to account for bias in the physics
 495 component. We compare the performance of REANA_DP and NorESM_DP, which both
 496 use default model parameters but with REANA_DP constraining the ocean’s physical state
 497 towards a monthly varying climatology – thus reducing its bias. The monthly climatological
 498 observations (ocean physics and BGC) are used for verification. Error in NorESM_DP
 499 temperature and salinity is large and similar every year (Figure 1). REANA_DP rapidly
 500 reduces error in temperature and salinity and sustains it at a low level (to about 44% for
 501 temperature and 50% for salinity. The climatology profiles of REANA_DP are also in better
 502 agreement with WOA18 climatology than in NorESM_DP (Figure 1c,f).

Figure 1. Hovmöller diagram of global monthly RMSE in NorESM_DP (left column) and REANA_DP (middle column) computed against WOA18 climatological temperature (top) and salinity (bottom). The black dotted and solid lines represent the monthly vertically-averaged RMSE (right y-axis) in NorESM_DP and REANA_DP, respectively. NorESM_DP is used as a reference here, and its vertically-averaged RMSE line is added to both panels. The vertical temperature and salinity climatology profiles are shown in the right column.

503 REANA_DP yields a pronounced improvement initially for phosphate, nitrate and oxy-
 504 gen (see Figure 2) within the first two years – this is particularly evident below 400 m.
 505 However, after that period, the error starts to grow in the top 500 meters, and the vertically
 506 and globally averaged RMSE is degraded after 10 years. A similar behaviour is also evident
 507 for dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC), silicate and total alkalinity (TA) (Figure 3). The
 508 degradation is quickest for silicate, for which the overall error is already degraded after a
 509 couple of years, while there are still overall improvements for alkalinity after ten years. The
 510 errors below ≈ 500 m are consistently reduced for DIC, TA and silicate in the REANA_DP
 511 experiment.

Figure 2. Global Hovmöller diagram of RMSE in NorESM_DP (column-1), REANA_DP (column-2), REANA_GP (column-3) and REANA_SP (column-4) computed against WOA18 monthly climatology of phosphate, nitrate and oxygen (shown in rows 1 to 3, respectively). The lines are the vertically monthly averaged RMSE (right y-axis). The vertical climatology profiles of phosphate, nitrate, and oxygen from each experiment and WOA18 are depicted in the rightmost column.

512 To investigate the degradation issue, we further examine the REANA_DP nutrients
 513 spatial distribution in the euphotic zone (0-100 m). REANA_DP brings an excessive con-
 514 centration of nutrients (phosphate and nitrate) to the euphotic zone (see Figure 4), which is
 515 too high almost everywhere in the globe. Phosphate and nitrate concentrations are higher
 516 over the Atlantic than in other regions (Figure 4c,h). Consequently, the REANA_DP ex-
 517 hibits higher phytoplankton growth and primary production rate than the NorESM_DP (not
 518 shown). Regions experiencing elevated phytoplankton growth accumulate larger amounts of

Figure 3. Same as Figure 2 but for silicate, dissolved inorganic carbon and total alkalinity.

519 particulate organic matter, which subsequently sinks to deeper ocean layers. This increases
 520 the input of organic matter and leads to enhanced remineralization, which consumes oxy-
 521 gen and releases nutrients. The enhanced remineralization in REANA_DP leads to oxygen
 522 depletion below the euphotic layer, which further increases the negative oxygen bias at inter-
 523 mediate ocean depths (approximately 100-500 meters) in biologically-active regions (Figure
 524 4r). In summary, reducing bias in ocean physics leads to increased nutrient transport to the
 525 ocean surface, improving the subsurface nutrient distribution (Figure 2b,g). However, the
 526 accumulation of nutrients in surface waters stimulates drift in near-surface layers over time.

527 In addition to the mean states, as presented so far, we also evaluate the performance
 528 of the seasonal cycle in the upper-ocean process (biological production and air-sea CO₂
 529 fluxes). The biases in the seasonal cycle of biological production have been identified as one
 530 of the key factors contributing to the uncertainty in projected carbon sinks and storage in
 531 the ESMs participating in CMIP5/6 (Kessler & Tjiputra, 2016; Goris et al., 2018; Rodgers
 532 et al., 2023), and their improvements have been prioritized in recent model development
 533 (J. F. Tjiputra et al., 2020).

534 For primary production, the NorESM_DP simulates considerably lower winter produc-
 535 tion (January–March in the Northern Hemisphere and July–September in the Southern
 536 Hemisphere) within the extratropical oceans (between 30° and 65°N and south of 30°S)
 537 compared to observational data (Figure 5a,b). Further, NorESM_DP simulates an exces-

Figure 4. WOA18 climatological estimate of (a) phosphate, (f) nitrate and (k) silicate averaged over euphotic zone (0-100 m depth) and over 100-500 m depth for oxygen. The second column depicts the corresponding climatological biases [2017-2026] in NorESM_DP. The third, fourth and fifth columns are for REANA_DP, REANA_GP and REANA_SP, respectively.

538 sively strong spring bloom over the Southern Ocean and has lower production in the tropical
 539 region relative to the observed estimates. REANA_DP enhances primary production near
 540 the equator but tends to overestimate the seasonal blooms in temperate regions of both
 541 hemispheres (Figure 5c). Notably, in the Northern Hemisphere, the bloom initiates too
 542 early: in February as opposed to April in the observations. The production is also too
 543 strong in the Southern Hemisphere, extending from the equator to the extratropical region,
 544 a behavior that significantly deviates from NorESM_DP and observational data.

545 We also analyze the sea-air CO₂ fluxes (Figure 5, row-2). NorESM_DP performs well
 546 in representing the seasonal cycle of sea-air CO₂ fluxes. However, REANA_DP significantly
 547 degrades its performance compared to NorESM_DP in the tropical and Southern Hemisphere
 548 regions due to an overestimation of outgassing. This issue, which is consistent with the
 549 higher upwelling rate (i.e., of carbon-rich deep water to the surface), is also evident from
 550 the high RMSE values (Figure 5l).

Figure 5. Hovmöller plots of the zonally averaged seasonal cycle of (a) observed climatology of primary production, and corresponding simulated climatology based on 2017-2026 period for (b-e) NorESM_DP, REANA_DP, REANA_GP and REANA_SP, respectively, together with (f) latitudinal varying RMSE from all experiments. The RMSE is computed using longitudinal and monthly climatology data. (g-l) same as for primary production but for sea-air CO₂ fluxes. Negative values show a sink to sea, whereas positive values indicated net outgassing of CO₂ fluxes from the ocean.

Figure 6. Global RMSE profile for monthly climatological [2017-2026] value of (a) phosphate (b) Nitrate (c) Oxygen (d) Silicate (e) dissolved inorganic carbon and (f) total alkalinity in all four experiments NorESM_DP (black dashed lines), REANA_DP (black solid lines), REANA_GP (purple lines) and REANA_SP (magenta lines).

551 The above results suggest that while reducing the ocean physical bias yields some benefit
 552 initially, the performance is degraded overall as the default BGC parameters are tuned to
 553 compensate for the biases in the ocean physics. Tuning BGC parameters to account for
 554 bias in the physical components is challenging when developing community code such as an
 555 Earth System Model. When bias in the physical ocean model is reduced, the performance of

556 the BGC model may degrade unless the BGC parameters are re-tuned (Löptien & Dietze,
 557 2019). However, as large biases in ocean physics lead to inaccuracies in representing BGC
 558 processes and their interactions, we can expect to achieve superior performance by re-tuning
 559 the BGC parameters by constraining errors in the physical ocean model.

560 **6.2 Offline global and spatial BGC parameter estimation**

561 We present the globally uniform (GP) and spatially varying (SP) estimated parameter
 562 values resulting from the offline iterative ensemble smoother technique.

563 Table 1 reports the default and ensemble mean of global estimated values for the five
 564 chosen BGC parameters. Figure 7 displays the initial probability density function of the
 565 PP ensemble as well as for GP after 1 and 2 iterations. In Iteration-1, two parameters, the
 566 half-saturation constant for nutrient uptake (K_N) and the remineralization rate (R_{poc}), ex-
 567 hibit a reduction (of 49% and 60%, respectively) from their default values. The remaining
 568 three parameters, the maximum grazing rate (G_{max}), the sinking speed (W_{poc}), and the
 569 half-saturation constant for silicate uptake (K_{Si}), are increased (by 13%, 20% and 68%,
 570 respectively). The estimated values from Iteration-2 demonstrate changes in a similar di-
 571 rection as Iteration-1, except for the remineralization rate, which shows nearly no changes
 572 between Iteration-1 and -2.

573 The spatial distributions of the parameter values obtained from the offline spatial pa-
 574 rameter estimation method in Iteration-1 are shown in Figure 8. Changes in the parameter
 575 values are significant for all five parameters compared to their default ones. Some param-
 576 eters exceeded the specified upper or lower boundaries (i.e., within 60% and 200% of the
 577 default values), and were enforced to remain within these ranges in a post-processing step.
 578 Some regional patterns clearly emerge from the map of all parameters. The estimates from
 579 the biologically active regions are in agreement with the global estimation. Singh et al.
 580 (2022) found that the NorESM model is merely insensitive to parameter values in the less
 581 biologically-active regions, and we should thus be cautious in over-interpreting parameter
 582 values there. Increased values of the sinking speed parameter can be seen over many biolog-
 583 ically active regions, which agrees well with the global estimation. Similarly, lower values
 584 for the remineralization rate are found over most regions, which also aligns with the global
 585 estimate.

586 **6.3 Impact of estimated BGC parameters on BGC climatology**

587 We evaluate the impact of the estimated BGC parameters from Iteration-1 on the BGC
 588 state by re-running an ocean reanalysis with the spatially varying and global estimates from
 589 Iteration 1 (REANA_SP and REANA_GP). The ocean state is constrained to the monthly

Figure 7. Probability density distributions (PDFs) for the perturbed parameter ensembles (i.e., prior ensembles) and the global estimated ensembles from Iteration-1 and -2. The vertical lines indicate the parameters' default values (as in NorESM_DP).

Figure 8. Parameters values obtained with the spatial parameter estimation in the first iteration. The background color represents the percentage change from their default values for each parameter $[100 * (\text{estimated_value} - \text{default_value}) / \text{default_value}]$.

590 ocean climatology, and the performance is assessed against BGC monthly climatology. Per-
 591 formances are compared to those of the free run with the default parameter (NorESM_DP)

592 and the reanalysis with the default parameter (REANA_DP). We start by analyzing the
593 RMSE of the monthly climatology of phosphate, nitrate, and oxygen that were used for
594 the parameter estimation. Therefore, they are not independent variables for evaluating the
595 performance of estimated parameters. In contrast, the monthly climatologies of silicate,
596 DIC, TA, primary production and CO₂ flux have not been used and can be considered
597 independent.

598 REANA_GP improves the performance of all state variables used in the parameter
599 estimation and effectively mitigates the drifting issues observed with default parameters
600 (Figures 2, 6, and Table 4). The drift in performance that led to a degradation in the
601 surface down to approximately 500 m in REANA_DP is also reduced. Errors continue to
602 decrease for phosphate and nitrate, while the error reduction stabilizes in oxygen. The
603 vertically integrated error settles at a lower error level than in NorESM_DP. Similar im-
604 provements are also found for the independent variables DIC and TA (Figures 3, 6). The
605 global error in REANA_GP is reduced by 15.6%, 16.4%, 7.9%, 7.7% and 1.9% for phosphate,
606 nitrate, oxygen, dissolved inorganic carbon and total alkalinity, respectively, in comparison
607 with NorESM_DP (Table 4). However, REANA_GP degrades performance compared to
608 NorESM_DP and even REANA_DP for silicate. It is unexpected to see improvements in
609 nitrate and phosphate and degradation in silicate, which suggests an internal inconsistency
610 between the formulation of the silicate cycle and other nutrients in the ocean BGC model.
611 This is analyzed in more detail below.

612 REANA_GP reduces the error spatially nearly everywhere compared to REANA_DP,
613 and also reduces the error compared to NorESM_DP (Figures 9, 10). This is important
614 because it implies that the model with reduced bias in ocean physics and re-tuned param-
615 eters can perform better than the default model. We previously observed that REANA_DP
616 accumulates excessive nutrients in the upper ocean layers. In REANA_GP, this issue is ef-
617 fectively mitigated, and phosphate and nitrate concentrations are reduced (Figure 4c,d,h,i).
618 The phosphate and nitrate concentration dynamics are primarily influenced by three param-
619 eters considered in this study: the half-saturation constant for nutrient uptake, the sinking
620 speed, and the remineralization rate. The estimated value of the half-saturation constant
621 for nutrient parameter is notably lower than the default values in the REANA_GP (as listed
622 in Table 1), facilitating the higher consumption of near-surface phosphate and nitrate con-
623 centrations for phytoplankton growth compared to the default values. Additionally, the
624 increase in the sinking speed accelerates the export of organic matter (containing an excess
625 of nutrients) from the surface into the deeper ocean. Similarly, the third parameter, the
626 remineralization rate, is reduced substantially, slowing the pace of nutrients released into
627 the deeper ocean. This reduces the nutrient availability in the ocean interior, leading to

628 reduced nutrient transport to the surface. These three estimated parameter values jointly
 629 act to balance phosphate and nitrate concentrations at the surface, preventing the excessive
 630 accumulation observed in REANA_DP. Consequently, this leads to improved phosphate and
 631 nitrate concentrations in the euphotic zones, showing the adequate impact of the parameter
 632 adjustment.

Figure 9. Average of RMSE in the top 800 m, (Row-1) for NorESM_DP monthly climatology [2017-2026] of (a) phosphate, (g) nitrate, and (m) oxygen. the second row shows the RMSE difference between NorESM_DP and REANA_DP (green colour indicates that REANA_DP outperforms NorESM_DP). Similarly, the third and fourth rows display the RMSE difference of NorESM_DP with that of REANA_GP and REANA_SP. Finally, rows five and six depict the RMSE difference of NorESM_DP with that of REANA_GP and REANA_SP.

Figure 10. Same as Figure 9 but for silicate, dissolved inorganic carbon and total alkalinity.

633 Excess surface nutrients in REANA_DP induce high phytoplankton growth, which leads
 634 to excessive oxygen depletion below the mixed layer through organic matter remineraliza-
 635 tion. One parameter that indirectly regulates phytoplankton growth is the maximum zoo-
 636 plankton grazing rate, which is increased in REANA_GP. This, combined with reduced
 637 surface levels of nutrients, reduces the primary production in upper oceans. As such,
 638 REANA_GP compares more favorably with observations than REANA_DP (not shown).
 639 Furthermore, this reduces the flux of particulate organic carbon and oxygen consumption
 640 below the mixed layer (in REANA_GP) and further alleviates the anomalously low oxygen
 641 simulated in the tropical upwelling system (REANA_DP; Figure 4r,s).

642 As reported above, for silicate, a slight degradation is seen in REANA_GP compared
 643 to REANA_DP (Figure 4n) and a strong degradation is found compared to NorESM_DP.
 644 It suggests that the degradation caused by correcting the ocean’s physical bias could not
 645 be counteracted by adjusting the parameters selected. Hence, our selection of BGC pa-
 646 rameters was tailored to focus on the carbon cycle and have negligible impact on silicate.
 647 Among the parameters selected for study here, only the half-saturation constant for silicate
 648 uptake can influence the surface silicate. Our global parameter estimation resulted in an
 649 increase of the half-saturation constant parameter, which led to a reduction of the silicate
 650 uptake during biogenic opal production and resulted in increasing surface silicate compared
 651 to REANA_GP. Another factor contributing to the silicate degradation is the reduction of
 652 phytoplankton concentrations, which implicitly reduces diatom production in REANA_GP
 653 compared to REANA_DP. This leads to an excess of surface silicate concentrations as di-
 654 atom consumes silicate. There are several approaches in which we can improve the silicate
 655 simulation. One would be to include the silicate observations in the parameter estimation.
 656 Another possibility is to extend the list of selected parameters to include those influencing
 657 the silicate cycle. For instance, the vertical sinking speed of biogenic opal (W_{opal}) and deep
 658 remineralization constant for the opal (R_{opal}) in the HAMOCC model will have a compa-
 659 rable impact on silicate than what W_{poc} and R_{poc} (used in this study) has on the nitrate
 660 cycle at depth.

661 The simulation REANA_SP, which uses spatial varying parameters, overall demon-
 662 strates very comparable performance to REANA_GP (Figures 2, 3, 4, 9, and 10). The
 663 North Atlantic stands out as a region where REANA_SP has improved performance com-
 664 pared to REANA_GP (for example, nitrate, Figures 9i,j). Conversely, performances are
 665 degraded compared to REANA_GP in the Southern Ocean. This coincides well with the
 666 density of the observation network, which is much higher in the North Atlantic than in
 667 the rest of the domain and that is particularly poor in the Southern Ocean. We suspect
 668 that the estimation period is too short and that the estimation fails in regions where the
 669 monthly climatological estimates are inaccurate (due to a lack of data), and their associated
 670 uncertainty is underestimated.

671 For primary production, REANA_GP and REANA_SP improve the performance com-
 672 pared to REANA_DP and NorESM_DP (Figure 5d,e), particularly in the tropical and the
 673 Southern Ocean. The pattern correlation is also increased, and the RMSE is lower in
 674 REANA_GP and REANA_SP than in REANA_DP (Figure 5f). Both REANA_GP and
 675 REANA_SP enhance winter production (particularly within the Southern Hemisphere) and
 676 exhibit improvements during all seasons in the tropics. Moreover, spatially varying parame-
 677 ter estimation (REANA_SP) demonstrates a better Southern Hemisphere spring bloom than

Table 4. Depth-averaged (0–800 m) global RMS error [$mmol\ m^{-3}$] for the BGC simulated climatology (2017–2026) in the NorESM_DP, REANA_DP, REANA_GP, and REANA_SP experiments (columns 2–5, respectively). The percentage error reduction relative to NorESM_DP is shown in parentheses. Green indicates improvement, while red indicates degradation compared to the free reference run NorESM_DP.

Variables (0–800 m)	RMSE	RMSE (% error reduction w.r.t. NorESM_DP)		
	NorESM_DP	REANA_DP	REANA_GP	REANA_SP
Phosphate	0.50	0.48 (4.0%)	0.42 (15.7%)	0.44 (12.9%)
Nitrate	6.4	6.3 (2.3%)	5.4 (16.4%)	5.7 (12.3%)
Oxygen	38.3	37.8 (1.3%)	35.3 (7.9%)	35.9 (6.1%)
Silicate	13.4	13.9 (-4.1%)	14.4 (-7.4%)	14.6 (-8.4%)
Dissolved Inorganic Carbon	75.0	67.0 (10.6%)	61.9 (17.5%)	63.1 (15.8%)
Total Alkalinity	36.7	34.4 (6.0%)	33.8 (7.8%)	33.9 (7.5%)

678 the global estimates (REANA_GP). In fact, REANA_SP shows the lowest RMSE compared
679 to the other three experiments for the southern bloom (Figure 5f).

680 The seasonal cycle of sea-air CO₂ fluxes is also improved in REANA_GP and RE-
681 ANA_SP, and they correct the degradation seen in REANA_DP in the tropical and South-
682 ern Hemisphere (Figure 5). While a slight degradation is observed in the high latitudes
683 of the Northern Hemisphere, both estimated parameter simulations slightly improve the
684 pattern correlation compared to NorESM_DP (0.68, 0.53, 0.72, and 0.71 for NorESM_DP,
685 REANA_DP, REANA_GP, and REANA_SP, respectively). REANA_GP performs slightly
686 better than REANA_SP in the tropics. This underscores the improvement achieved through
687 the estimated parameters in simulating the mean seasonal variations in CO₂ fluxes.

688 To conclude, we can see that the parameter estimation clearly improves performance
689 compared to both simulations with default parameters (NorESM_DP and REANA_DP)
690 already after the first iteration. A small degradation remains near the surface (Figure 6).
691 The global parameter estimation provides overall better and more stable performance. We
692 will, therefore, continue with that scheme and assess whether further improvements can be
693 achieved with a second iteration.

694 **6.4 Impact of a second iteration with global parameter estimation**

695 We now analyze the impact of running a second iteration with global parameter esti-
696 mation on the BGC monthly climatology. We analyze the performance of REANA_GP2,
697 which is a reanalysis produced with the parameter estimated from REANA_GP output in
698 the second iteration (Section 2.3 and 4) and assimilate the monthly ocean temperature and
699 salinity climatology. It should be noted that we have not increased the observation error for

700 the two iterations as we should from the DA theory with the iterative ensemble smoother
 701 (Section 2.3). The reason is that there is a large uncertainty on the BGC monthly clima-
 702 tology observation error. We view the multi-iteration as a way to iterate until performance
 703 degrades for independent data (criteria for stopping iteration).

704 We focus on the top 100 m where REANA_GP shows a degradation compared to
 705 NorESM_DP. The performance below that depth is nearly identical between REANA_GP
 706 and REANA_GP2 (not shown). The REANA_GP2 RMSE profiles in the 0-100 m depth
 707 range show some improvements over REANA_GP, particularly for phosphate, nitrate and
 708 DIC (Figure 11). The reduction is most pronounced for phosphate in the surface and sub-
 709 surface layers of the Northern Hemisphere and tropical regions. For nitrate, REANA_GP2
 710 matches the performance of NorESM_DP near the surface in the tropical regions. The im-
 711 provement of REANA_GP over NorESM_DP for oxygen is further enhanced, particularly for
 712 the Southern Hemisphere. However, there is no improvement in silicate and total alkalinity
 713 (not shown). Nevertheless, we can conclude that the second iteration has further reduced
 714 the error. The improvement of the second iteration may relate to the capability of the IES
 715 to better handle the non-linear response of the model parameters (Evensen, 2018) or to
 716 the effective reduction of observation error caused by the second iteration. While we could
 717 have continued with more iterations, we stopped here as the error reduction is already much
 718 smaller than the first iteration.

719 **6.5 Performance of the global estimated parameters with time-varying ocean** 720 **constraint**

721 The estimation and verification of the parameters have until now been done with the
 722 ocean physics constrained towards a monthly climatology. We verify whether the improve-
 723 ments are sustained in a reanalysis that assimilates time-varying ocean temperature and
 724 salinity profiles – i.e., in a system that depicts realistic time variability but where the ocean
 725 physics state is still sustained at a low error level. The reanalysis REANA_IAV_GP2 ex-
 726 periments are conducted for 1985-2022 with the BGC parameters obtained from Iteration-2
 727 (Section 4) and assimilating time-varying physical observations. As BGC observations are
 728 lacking, we will still perform our validation towards BGC monthly climatology, and the
 729 reanalysis is validated for the period 1993–2022 to leave the system time to adjust to the
 730 new parameters (Section 4).

731 The results are in overall agreement with the previous analysis (Figure 12). The errors
 732 in the REANA_IAV_GP2 climatological BGC mean state profiles are substantially reduced
 733 for all variables except for silicate that is still degraded near the surface compared to the
 734 NorESM_DP (as previously). Interestingly, the degradation at the surface compared to

Figure 11. Northern Hemisphere (NH; column-1), Tropics (TP; column-2), Southern Hemisphere (SH; column-3) and global (column-4) mean vertical RMSE profile for climatology [2017-2026] phosphate (row-1), nitrate (row-2), oxygen (row-3) and dissolved inorganic carbon (row-4). The profiles are extended from the surface to 100 m depths (euphoric zone) for NorESM_DP (black dashed lines), REANA_DP (black solid lines), REANA_GP (purple lines) and REANA_GP2 (dashed purple lines).

735 NorESM_DP for phosphate and nitrate is no longer noticeable. We suspect that the as-
 736 simulation of a WOA monthly climatology of temperature and salinity introduces an error
 737 term near the surface (related to interannual variability during the reference period). This
 738 shows that assimilating observations directly within our system is beneficial. Compared to
 739 NorESM_DP, REANA_IJV_GP2 shows a reduction in the overall RMS errors by 20%, 18%,
 740 7%, 27%, and 17% for phosphate, nitrate, oxygen, dissolved inorganic carbon and total
 741 alkalinity, in the top 800 m.

742 This comparison is highly promising, considering that the model with default param-
 743 eters was carefully tuned to get the best possible fit with observations and contributed to
 744 CMIP6.

Figure 12. Global mean vertical RMSE profile for climatology [averaged over 1993-2022] (a) phosphate (b) Nitrate (c) Oxygen (d) Silicate (e) dissolved inorganic carbon and (f) total alkalinity in NorESM_DP (black dashed lines) and REANA_IAV_GP2 (orange solid lines).

745 7 Summary and conclusions

746 Improving the ocean biogeochemical state’s spatio-temporal simulation in a fully cou-
 747 pled Earth System Model (ESM) is challenging because there are multiple sources of error,
 748 and the parameters’ sensitivities are interlinked. Data assimilation methods such as the
 749 Ensemble Kalman Filter have recently been shown to offer a semi-automatic (i.e., with lim-
 750 ited human intervention) and efficient framework for optimizing these parameters (Simon
 751 et al., 2012; Simon & Bertino, 2012; Simon et al., 2015; Gharamti, Samuelsen, et al., 2017;
 752 Gharamti, Tjiputra, et al., 2017; Singh et al., 2022; Mammun et al., 2022). They can esti-
 753 mate multiple parameters jointly based on several observation data sets and consider their
 754 respective uncertainty. Such methods were tested for the first time with a full ESM in an
 755 idealized twin experiment framework (Singh et al., 2022) and demonstrated great potential.
 756 Here, we follow on Singh et al. (2022) and demonstrate, for the first time, the potential of
 757 an ensemble data assimilation method to estimate BGC parameters within an ESM in a
 758 real framework (i.e., assimilating real observations).

759 We use the NorCPM system, which combines the NorESM model with ensemble data
 760 assimilation methods. We focus on five key BGC parameters influencing the ocean carbon

761 cycle and use an iterative ensemble smoother for the parameter estimation. We assimilate
762 BGC climatological observations in offline mode – on an existing ensemble of simulations
763 with perturbed parameters – to jointly estimate a set of BGC parameters. The chosen
764 parameters characterize the major surface biological processes such as nutrient uptake for
765 phytoplankton growth, zooplankton grazing, sinking and remineralization of organic matter.

766 A key challenge with tuning the model is that these parameters may have been tuned to
767 compensate for errors not intrinsic to the component to which the parameter belongs. Ocean
768 physics plays a significant role in driving the ocean BGC variability. Here, we show that
769 maintaining a low level of error in ocean physics initially leads to a substantial reduction of
770 the BGC error. However, this initial strong reduction is followed by subsequent error growth
771 near the surface due to excessive nutrient upwelling. This suggests that BGC parameters
772 in our version of NorESM have been tuned to compensate for oceanic physical biases.

773 We have tested two versions of parameter estimation, one with globally uniform pa-
774 rameters and one where parameters can vary spatially. The parameters are estimated based
775 on the error of monthly climatology estimates of nitrate, phosphate and oxygen from a
776 coupled reanalysis, that assimilates the monthly climatologies of temperature and salinity.
777 Rerunning the reanalysis with updated parameters shows that both versions yield substan-
778 tial improvements for quantities used in the parameter estimation and also for independent
779 quantities (total alkalinity, dissolved inorganic carbon, sea-air CO₂ fluxes and primary pro-
780 duction). A degradation is found for silicate, which primarily relates to our selection of BGC
781 parameters that cannot fully regulate the silicate cycle. Overall, reanalysis with global pa-
782 rameter estimates performed better than the one with spatially-varying parameters. This
783 is likely a consequence of inaccuracy in the monthly climatological observations of BGC in
784 regions where data is very sparse (such as in the Southern Ocean) and an underestimation
785 of the observation error. Using several iterations to estimate global parameters can improve
786 the result, but the benefit seems to have nearly converged already after two iterations. Fi-
787 nally, a long coupled reanalysis was performed from 1982-2022, assimilating time-varying
788 monthly temperature and salinity observations, and using the globally-uniform updated pa-
789 rameters. The parameter estimation reduces the error of BGC in the coupled reanalysis by
790 20%, 18%, 7%, 27%, and 17% for phosphate, nitrate, oxygen, dissolved inorganic carbon
791 and total alkalinity, respectively, compared to a reanalysis run with the default parameter
792 values. This demonstrates that the improvements seen for a configuration that is forced to
793 follow climatological variability are also verified in a configuration for which ocean physics
794 has a realistic time variability and with transient historical forcing.

795 This study highlights the potential of our parameter estimation framework to enhance
796 the performance of an ESM. The method can ingest as many observations as available and

797 optimally account for the respective uncertainty of the observation and model. It can also
798 converge with multiple parameters simultaneously and with the coupled model that will be
799 used at the end. This practice differs from the conventional approach, where uncertain pa-
800 rameters from each model component are often estimated in forced configuration (i.e., with
801 prescribed boundary conditions rather than in coupled mode) and in isolation (one param-
802 eter at a time). Some of these parameters need to be re-tuned in the coupled configuration,
803 which requires substantial human and computational resources. Our proposed approach is
804 semi-automated, i.e., it requires few human decisions, unlike conventional manual tuning,
805 and, in principle, can be applied for different model components simultaneously. The itera-
806 tive ensemble smoother simplifies the portability of the method to other models. One only
807 needs to implement the input/output routines (reading and writing of the model variables
808 and parameters) within the data assimilation code to apply the method.

809 Our study aimed at estimating parameters in the system when we constrain the bias
810 in the physical ocean model. Another test (not presented here) found that a comparable
811 improvement can be achieved without correcting the physical bias –i.e., adjusting BGC
812 model parameters from an ensemble of perturbed free runs (without constraint on the bias
813 of the ocean component) of ESMs. This test was conducted solely to demonstrate the
814 effectiveness of our proposed parameter estimation method. However, we do not recommend
815 this approach, as neglecting ocean physics bias is a way to compensate for model bias – i.e.,
816 tuning the BGC parameters to compensate for errors in the physical model component.
817 This approach brings no guarantee that the system will show the best performance in the
818 future (e.g., climate projections, Löptien and Dietze (2019)) as bias compensation may
819 overfit the condition for which parameters were tuned. Furthermore, in community-driven
820 codes like ESMs, where distinct teams develop and maintain individual components, tuning
821 parameters to compensate for biases across components can hinder progress. In this case,
822 reducing errors in one component (e.g., ocean, atmosphere) will then result in degraded
823 performance for the other components unless a full re-tuning of the system parameter is
824 performed. Instead, we advocate that a more robust approach is to optimize each ESM
825 component parameter by sustaining the bias to a low level in the other model components.
826 Such a framework minimizes the risk of reciprocal bias compensation and thus provides a
827 more robust estimate of the skill of our system. Furthermore, improvements in individual
828 components should directly result in a gain for the other components, without a need for re-
829 tuning the system. This should lead to a more proactive attitude to upgrading components
830 in the community ESM code. Note that, in this study we have only constrained errors in
831 the ocean physics, but depending on the objectives, e.g., improving the representation of
832 air-sea CO₂ fluxes, including land and atmospheric constraints could be valuable. This is

833 now possible with the recent development of NorCPM (Nair et al., 2024; Garcia-Oliva et
834 al., 2023).

835 Unlike in Singh et al. (2022), we had to reduce the complexity of our ensemble data
836 assimilation method (with the iterative ensemble smoother rather than the dual one step
837 ahead smoother), and we pursued global estimates rather than spatially varying ones. These
838 were motivated by the challenges of our application – which are characterized by sparse
839 and inaccurate observations in some locations, variability and error dominated by sporadic
840 events and slower sensitivity to model parameters compared to error growth from other
841 independent sources. We are still confident that with an improved observation network, one
842 should be able to achieve superior performance with spatially varying parameters.

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855 **Data Availability Statement**

856 Model simulations presented in this article have been organized and made available. It
857 contains a separate section for each of the experiments presented (NorESM_DP, NorESM_PP,
858 REANA_DP, REANA_PP, REANA_GP, REANA_SP, REANA_GP2 and REANA_IAP_GP2).
859 Each folder contains the ensemble mean outputs from the ensemble simulations in NetCDF
860 format. The full simulations will be made available on <https://archive.sigma2.no> with a
861 specific doi upon acceptance of the manuscript. To retrieve the simulations, one can use the
862 following link (700 GB):

863 `wget -c https://ns9039k.web.sigma2.no/datapeak/ParameterEstimation.tar.gz`

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